

RESEARCHING THE METHODS OF ASSESSING THE FINANCIAL POSITION OF AN ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. *The information base is considered for the analysis of the financial condition. Assessing the financial position of an enterprise is a key task for management, investors and creditors, allowing to understand the sustainability of the business, its ability to generate profit and manage risks. This article considers the main methods of assessing the financial condition of enterprises, their advantages and disadvantages. The main points of the methods of analyzing the financial condition, as well as a brief overview of their features are discussed.*

Keywords: *financial analysis; financial condition; analysis of the financial condition; enterprise development strategy; analysis methods.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest the most important aspect of the economic activity of an enterprise is its financial position. It has a significant impact on the stability and efficiency of the enterprise; its financial position determines its ability to business cooperation and assesses the degree of ensuring the economic interests of partners and the enterprise. Balance sheet allows to assess the structure of assets and liabilities, as well as the ratio of equity and debt capital. This helps to determine the financial stability of the enterprise. Income and expense analysis allows you to assess the profitability of the business. It is important to pay attention to the dynamics of profit and the ratio of various income and expense items. Cash flow assessment helps to understand the liquidity of the enterprise and its ability to fulfill obligations. It is possible to identify current and emerging problems and bring them to the attention of the enterprise management by analyzing its financial position. It helps to develop tactics and strategy for enterprise growth, justify management decisions and plans, control their implementation, identify reserves for increasing production efficiency, evaluate the activities of the enterprise, its divisions and employee activities. The first step in financial analysis is to assess the financial position, which is carried out primarily using information from financial statements, as well as provided explanations and any relevant external data. Ignoring these elements leads to an inaccurate assessment of the company's financial stability. The relevance of the topic in this regard is beyond doubt.

Problem. The main objective of assessing the financial condition of an organization is the timely detection and elimination of shortcomings in financial and economic activities. In this case, special attention should be paid to finding reserves to increase its solvency and financial stability. In practice, external and internal analysis are usually distinguished. The company's employees directly conduct the internal analysis. External analysts, like audit firms, conduct external analysis. Internal analysis is a study of how capital is formed, structured, allocated and used in order to identify reserves for strengthening and maintaining the financial position of the enterprise, increasing profitability indicators and expanding the enterprise's own sources of financing. The results of internal analysis are used to forecast indicators of the financial position of the enterprise, as well as for planning and controlling operations. The financial position of the enterprise is studied through external analysis to assess the level of risk associated with capital investments and

establish potential profitability. Investors and credit institutions that monitor the compliance of financial statements conduct external analysis.

Solution. The main source of information for studying the composition and location of capital and assets of the enterprise, as well as for determining business performance indicators is the report and balance sheet of the financial sector. The balance sheet shows three consecutive reporting dates, providing information on the position of capital, property and liabilities to third parties. Numerous attributes are used to assess the financial position of an enterprise, and it is with their help that you can most thoroughly and accurately determine the position of the enterprise in both the internal and external environment. Analysis of the structure and quality of assets and liabilities, compliance of the management structure with the activities carried out, justification of expenses, reflection of income, analysis of the profit indicator, general and individual types of activities of the enterprise, distribution of profit, use of created reserves are the main direction of the analysis of the financial position. Calculation of financial indicators of solvency, financial stability and commercial activity is the basis for the analysis of the financial position of the enterprise. Graphical, tabular and ratio approaches are part of the methodology used to analyze the financial position of the enterprise. The general financial position of the enterprise, as well as the financial condition of specific objects of financial analysis can be assessed using the graphical method of financial analysis.

Definitely, for subsequent assessment of the financial position of the enterprise in the past and present, as well as for forecasting the financial position in the future, it is carried out by using a graphical display in relative or absolute values of the financial statement indicators on the balance sheet chart at the beginning and end of the analyzed period [3,114]. Illustration of the relationship between the financial data of the organization is called a balance sheet chart. The ratio approach to financial analysis explains the financial proportions between various items of financial statements.

Method. The study uses several methods to determine the economic and financial health of enterprises. With some minor changes, the basic ideas and course of the analysis procedure remain the same. A set of analytical methods, known as analysis methodology, is used to determine the current state of its financial and economic operations.

It should be admitted that methods of financial analysis are divided into different categories. In the field of financial analysis, the main methods of checking financial statements are established:

1. Horizontal analysis involves analyzing the indicators of the dynamics structure and determining the dynamics indicators reflected in the reporting indicators for each item of the financial statements using the base period.

2. Establishing the structure of financial indicators and determining each item of the financial statements based on the final indicators of the organization's activities, which are reflected in the forms of financial statements, is called vertical (structural) analysis.

3. Identifying the main trend in the dynamics of indicators is the next stage of trend analysis, which involves comparing each reporting element with several previous periods [3,114].

4. Inter-industry comparison (comparison of the organization's indicators with those of competitors and with average industry indicators) and intra-company comparison (comparison of the main indicators of the organization, subsidiaries and structural divisions) are two categories of comparative analysis.

5. Analysis of the influence of individual factors (reporting elements) on the performance indicator under study is known as factor analysis. Financial statements are the main source of information used for financial analysis and financial position assessment.

Besides that, the advantage of this approach to financial position analysis is that it is easy to calculate. Using the ratio approach, the indicator is calculated and compared with the base. Analysis of indicators of the financial position of an enterprise is carried out to compare the financial positions of different enterprises and to find out how long-term changes in the position of the enterprise are.

Conclusion. It is not a secret that assessing the financial position of an enterprise is a complex process that requires the use of various methods and approaches. Each of them has its own advantages and disadvantages, and the choice of a specific method depends on the objectives of the analysis, the specifics of the business and the available data. A comprehensive approach to assessment will provide the most complete picture of the financial position of the enterprise and its future prospects. Financial ratios have the disadvantage that they are static and do not take into account differences in accounting methods and the quality of component indicators. Working with financial ratios includes various stages. The categories and characteristics necessary to shed light on a specific aspect of the financial position, such as solvency, are selected at the initial stage. At the second stage, indicators (ratios) are created, such as the overall solvency ratio, which quantitatively reflect the analyzed financial position. The study of the numerical values that the desired ratio can take is the goal of the third stage. The financial position of the position as a whole and the objects of its financial analysis are assessed synthetically based on the results of the analysis of the financial position of the enterprise using the previously mentioned methods. Synthetic assessment of the financial health of the enterprise is a generalization and explanation of the results that describe the topics of the financial health of the enterprise. The purpose of the synthetic assessment is to identify the most important quantitative and qualitative aspects of the actual values of financial indicators affecting the financial position of the enterprise [3,115]. General conclusions are made on the basis of a synthetic assessment of the financial position of the enterprise relative to the state of the objects of financial analysis and the overall financial position of the enterprise, as well as problems with the financial position of the enterprise and the available resources for their solution. The fact that financial accounting and reporting data are not up-to-date can lead to a distortion of the assessment of the financial position of the organization. Management accounting data and analysis are crucial for ensuring the current development of the financial health indicators of the organization.

By summarizing it should be suggested that modern methods of assessing the financial condition of an organization are of fundamental importance, but they are usually not applied in practice individually. Many enterprises use a combination of assessment methods when assessing the financial condition to ensure high accuracy of the analysis. While using a fully integrated strategy for assessing the financial condition of an enterprise, the limitations and disadvantages of various methodologies and methods are balanced. This is the reason for using an integrated approach to the analysis of the financial position.

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